

Jisc

**A review of
transitional
agreements
in the UK:
Executive
summary**

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Executive summary

Transitional agreements, adopted by Jisc and UK institutions alongside the global research community, were devised specially for hybrid journals operating both subscription and Open Access publishing models. Envisioned as a temporary mechanism to support publishers with transitioning titles to fully OA, they have the dual aim to “bring institutional investments in scholarly journal publishing under oversight and control, with an eye to cost reduction, and to drive a transition of scholarly journal publishing to Open Access”¹.

As of January 2024 Jisc has negotiated and/or renewed 75 TAs with 47 publishers; we launched the first in 2016 with Springer. During that time, the **sector's requirements for TAs**, governed by the **UUK Jisc content negotiation strategy group**, have been refined to reflect changes in funder and institutional policies and learnings from our negotiations and institutional implementation. As a result, our negotiations have secured improvements to TAs including greater read access and OA publishing coverage, adherence to standards and workflow improvements. Our negotiations for TAs have also pushed for publishers to provide transparency on their costs, pricing and plans to flip their journal portfolios to OA in recognition that TAs were intended to be 'temporary and transitional.'

Ten years on from when negotiations commenced for the first TA with Springer, this review evaluates how effective TAs have been in delivering an OA transition, explores the impact of TAs globally and – critically – assesses the extent to which they have achieved the UK HE sector's requirements.

The review responds to the following questions:

- What proportion of scholarly literature is Open Access?
- What impact have transitional agreements had on open access to global and UK research publications?
- What effect have transitional agreements had on costs for UK institutions?
- How far have transitional agreements facilitated author compliance with funder requirements?
- Do transitional agreements deliver on their promise of being temporary and transitional?

It presents an evidence base for discussion. We hope that the review and its findings act as a catalyst for the research sector and partners to collectively discuss their aims for the future of open research dissemination and chart their roadmap to achieve this.

Scope

Our review is large but we have deliberately structured it, and its methodology and data, so that others including institutions, consortia, publishers and funders can use and build on our findings.

In **section 1** we review key UK and international OA initiatives, declarations and government, funder and publisher policy developments. We consider the developments that led to TAs, including the advent of offsetting models that sought to address the rising costs of OA and subscription access.

Section 2 contains our analysis of rates of the transition to OA (global and UK); an analysis of publishers' output and journal titles flipping to OA and the transition to OA by subject.

Section 3 assesses TAs against iterations of sector requirements, including cost constraint, funder compliance, licence type selection and transparency through data analysis, and publisher and institutional case studies.

Section 4 contains our conclusions, including a series of recommended actions that can be taken to improve the performance of TAs or to address the broader concerns expressed during this review and our negotiations.

This review does not examine publishers' commercial strategies or provide a comparative discussion on each publisher's approach to OA. Neither do we explore author behaviours and the extent to which the availability of TAs influences their publication choices. We also do not consider how openness or publication volumes are currently valued in the reward and incentive structures of research-performing organisations including review, promotion or tenure decisions or policies.

Our negotiations have secured improvements to TAs including greater read access and OA publishing coverage, adherence to standards and workflow improvements.

We acknowledge that publishers, institutions and consortia globally and UK HEIs are at different stages in the transition to OA and that the review, particularly the article analysis in [section 2](#), represents a snapshot in time. For example, our largest TA by article volume (Elsevier) started in 2022 and we saw higher levels of opt outs of OA publishing in the initial months of the agreement as authors grew accustomed to the OA workflow.

Lastly, we would like readers to note that TAs are only one type of OA agreement, and we have and will continue to support diversity through the negotiation of a range of OA models.

Findings

In this section we present some of the core findings. We strongly encourage you to read the full report as this contains valuable context, including the factors that are likely to have contributed to the results. The timeline of our review covers the COVID-19 pandemic, which upended research in many fields while accelerating OA to research in others but especially biomedical research.²

What proportion of scholarly literature is Open Access?

The proportion and absolute numbers of global OA articles (Gold and Hybrid) have continued to grow over the last seven years, albeit slowing in 2022. Overall, the global proportion of Open articles published has increased over the last eight years, from 21% in 2014 to 46% in 2022.³

Despite this increase, the absolute number of Closed articles increased from 2.2 million to 2.6 million during the same period, likely due to the increase in overall research output. The growth in the proportion of Gold articles slowed to +0.9% between 2021 and 2022 after a steady growth of around 2.2% to 2.6% (2014 – 2019). Of concern is that after several years of a steady decline in the proportion of Closed articles, in 2022 it started to grow (+1%).

Gold articles make up the largest share of global OA output, averaging around four times the share of Hybrid. Between 2014 and 2022 Gold also grew considerably faster than Hybrid (by 19% compared to 5%), but this trend looks like it may now be switching, with proportions of Hybrid increasing faster and Gold growth slowing since 2020. The Green route to OA has also been declining across all the categories examined (Green-only, Gold and Green or Hybrid and Green), particularly in the more recent years.

In 2022, the proportion of UK Open articles was 4% higher when compared with the proportion of global Open articles.

UK transitioning to OA faster than the global rate

The UK's strong culture of publishing its research OA is reflected in our analysis. In 2022, the number of UK Open articles (all articles with any author affiliated with a UK organisation) was 4% higher when compared with the number of global Open articles (UK: 50%; global 46%). In addition, the UK has 15% fewer Closed articles (UK: 35%; global: 50%). In 2022 UK OA articles accounted for 65% of UK output (including Gold, Hybrid and Green), with a continual increase in absolute numbers and proportions of Open articles over the last eight years. Overall, the proportion of Open articles has increased by 30% and the proportion of Closed articles has decreased by 25% between 2014 and 2022.

However, the review also finds that in recent years (2021 and 2022) there has been a resurgence in (or at least, retention of) Closed articles. Closed UK articles grew by 4.5% between 2021 and 2022 after four years of decline. This growth must be monitored.

We observed important differences by subject: the UK publishes the most articles in medicine (slightly higher than the global average), but medicine is eighth lowest in its uptake of OA (compared with fourth highest globally).⁴ Overall, the median share of UK OA across subject areas is just under 40%, compared with 33% globally. For some fields such as engineering, environmental sciences and business and economics the proportion of Closed articles and Open articles has increased simultaneously due to a decline in Green-only content.

What impact have transitional agreements had on open access to global and UK research publications?

From 2018 to 2022 there was a more than 900% increase in the number of UK articles published under TAs with the same publishers, which is directly attributable to the increase in the number of TAs from one to 38 in the same period. TAs gave authors the ability to publish immediate OA at a time when most publisher embargo⁵ periods did not permit the deposit and sharing of the author accepted manuscript (AAM) – of the TA publishers covered by our review 32% offered compliant Green OA options as of July 2023. Between 2017 and 2022 we saw considerable growth in OA uptake in disciplines with lower levels of research funding, including the arts, humanities and social sciences (AHSS)⁶. TAs also facilitated immediate OA publishing for low-publishing HEIs.

Unintended consequences

While the UK appears to be transitioning to OA more effectively than the global average, there are some unintended consequences of TAs that are important to consider.

The UK's proportion of Hybrid articles is more than double the proportion in the rest of the world (UK: 21%; global: 10%). The UK's year-on-year increase in Hybrid publishing has recently surpassed the levels of growth in Gold publishing. This difference appears to be driven by TAs: the trend can be seen across all levels of our analysis, where the proportion of Hybrid articles in titles incorporated into TAs rose 19% between 2018 and 2022.

There has been a steady decline in the number of UK Green-only articles – around 4% over each of the last four years. This is a more exaggerated version of the global trend. While the UK had an initial emphasis on the Green route to OA (see section 1), we note that TAs appear to have converted articles to Gold/Hybrid OA that were likely to have previously been made OA via institutional or subject repositories. This may suggest that Gold and Hybrid routes are becoming more popular than – and even replacing – the repositories as a route to OA.

Closed content still dominates

Across global output in the TA titles of the 38 publishers we investigated, the shift toward Open was stronger than the (downward) shift in Closed – on average the proportion of Closed content declined by 2% and Open content increased by 7% for their TA titles. However, despite the downward shift, the average proportion of Closed content in the TA titles for the 38 publishers was 61% in 2022. This was not limited to just a few of the 38 publishers: 71% had proportions of Closed articles above 50% in their TA titles. The data was also reviewed at the UK corresponding author (CA) level, and albeit at a smaller scale, the review finds that for 13 of Jisc TA publishers the proportion of Closed UK CA content in their TA titles actually increased or was maintained between the year preceding the TA and 2022.

While you would expect the proportion of Closed articles in TA titles to reduce, around 40% of UK CA output has remained behind a paywall for the last five years. An in-depth examination of why 40% of UK CA output remains behind a paywall was out of our review's scope but factors include the limited reach and uptake of TAs beyond UK HE (see section 2b). Other factors may include the launch of more fully OA journals at the expense of the conversion or flipping of hybrid journals and the continued growth of articles in TA titles.

What effect have transitional agreements had on costs for UK institutions?

TAs reduced and constrained costs at a sector level

TAs have been a successful mechanism to constrain costs when reviewing at the sector level. The 2022 Jisc TAs (excluding Springer Nature) have delivered actual cost savings of £16.7m to subscribing institutions in the first year of the agreement when compared to expenditure in the preceding year⁷.

Total 2022 expenditure via Jisc on TAs was £137m. Our analysis estimates that HEIs avoided costs of £6m in 2020 through TAs, (see section 3a) increasing to £42m in 2022 and a further £49.1m⁸ when modelled into 2024 (see figure 27). Another successful outcome of TAs is that they have provided affordable routes to publication for low-output institutions – as a result of the Wiley TA six institutions published under the agreement that had not published OA with Wiley previously⁹. TAs have also buffered high-output institutions from high publication fees when the APC route was the only funder compliant route for 68.4% of the TA publishers. However, we note

that real-terms savings and cost avoidance vary at the institutional level and it may be less easy to secure real terms savings in future, particularly if pricing is based on article volume and/or list price APCs.

Reliance on block grant funds

Even with estimated cost avoidance of nearly £42m in 2022, TA costs are still substantial. To aid institutions subscribing to TAs as a way of increasing OA and compliant publishing routes, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) has permitted use of its OA block grants towards TA fees¹⁰. We estimate that institutions used up to £9.4m of UKRI block grant funding towards the costs of TAs in 2022 – nearly a tenth of modelled costs for TAs that year. By 2024, this is predicted to increase to 25% of the modelled costs for 2024, faster than the predicted rate of increase of the modelled costs of TAs, meaning institutions stand to become increasingly reliant on the UKRI block grant to fund the costs of future TAs.

Longer term sustainability concerns

TAs repurpose previous subscription spend to cover the cost of read access and OA publishing. However, the APC persists as commercial publishers' preferred OA business model and the value of APCs is often used to calculate the cost of TAs.

As highlighted in [section 4](#) there are significant concerns with the longer term sustainability of article-based models. The zero VAT-rating for books, printed matter and e-publications in 2020 has had the effect of making the OA publishing charges that 'open up' access to research more costly than the equivalent fees to subscribe to the same content and read it. This, combined with the continued acceleration of published research articles ([see section 2](#)), means that OA models that are tied to

publication output are likely to prevent institutions from participating in the future, due to escalating costs.

How far have transitional agreements facilitated author compliance with funder requirements?

High levels of compliance achieved

TAs enabled the UK to achieve an exceptionally high level of compliance with funder OA policies – over 93% of UKRI-funded articles have a compliant route available to them¹¹ and, of these, 63% can be compliant through a Jisc-negotiated TA. Almost all TA publishers (35, or 92%) present a Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC BY) to authors as the default licence, with one publisher implementing systems to permit this from 2024.

Deposit in repositories

Almost all the Gold and Hybrid UK CA articles for the 38 TA publishers are also in a repository (and therefore REF-eligible¹²) but only 13 (34%) of the TA publishers support automatic deposit of Gold and Hybrid articles to institutional repositories. We discuss embargo periods and the uptake of institutional rights retention policies in [section 1](#).

The majority of publishers support UK funder policies by depositing articles to PubMed Central (PMC) and Europe PMC (EPMC) but the review has highlighted differences in approaches. For example, two publishers only deposit to funder-mandated repositories if an APC has been paid, whereas two other publishers deposit AAMs irrespective of whether the author or institution is part of a TA.

Reducing administrative burden?

Our work to simplify and streamline OA processes was intended to ensure that scaling up OA was not unduly burdensome for authors and OA administrators. Although one of our case study institutions reported that the scale of OA achieved via TAs would not be possible without such a centrally managed system, overall efficiencies delivered were variable and the administrative burden of OA management persists. The institutions we interviewed acknowledge that TAs have improved workflows, but variations in offers, processes and systems between TAs mean that TA management continues to be resource-intensive for institutions, requiring specialised staff and financial management.

Total 2022 expenditure via Jisc on TAs was £137m. Our analysis estimates that HEIs avoided costs of £6m in 2020 through TAs, increasing to £42m in 2022 and a further £49.1m when modelled into 2024.

Do TAs deliver on their promise of being temporary and transitional?

The rate of transition is slow

As the UK represents a small proportion of global articles (approximately 4% in 2022¹³) we would not expect Jisc TAs alone to have a material impact on a publisher's OA coverage. The increase in global TAs does not appear to have made a material impact on levels of OA, either. We observed low rates of journals being 'flipped' to fully OA between 2018 and 2022. Fifteen publishers flipped some TA titles (although generally less than 10%), but we estimate that two-thirds flipped no journals at all. Of the publishers we modelled Karger flipped the highest proportion of its titles to TA – 15% (14 titles). Of the 'big five' publishers Wiley flipped the greatest proportion of Jisc TA titles to OA – 7% (104 titles).

TAs appear to be a more successful transition strategy within the UK for smaller, society publishers with a smaller portfolio of titles [see section 2]. The top four publishers by volume (Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley and Taylor & Francis [T&F]), account for 58% of UK closed articles (2017 – 2022) and during the period of the review these publishers increased or maintained proportions of UK Closed articles in their TA titles. If TAs do not transition the portfolios of the top publishers by output, the OA transition will not go far or fast enough.

The influence of TAs is also limited by their article coverage: for the publishers examined in this review an increase in the number of global TAs has not yet translated into higher proportions of articles made OA via these TAs.

Based on the journal flipping rates observed between 2018 – 2022 it would take at least 70 years for the big five publishers to flip their TA titles to OA. While our analysis and inspection of conversion rates or 'flipping' from hybrid to fully gold suggest that we will not transition the current scholarly publishing system away from paywalls in an acceptable timescale, we acknowledge that it is both the sum and coverage of a critical mass of OA arrangements that will induce a transition. For example arrangements that cover all researchers and all output that are adapted to reflect local finances are more likely to 'move the dial' than an approach that focuses on a specific funder or sector eg. higher education institutions (HEIs).

Transparency remains unclear

The transitional agreements oversight group (TAOG)¹⁴, one of Jisc's strategic sector groups met with four¹⁵ TA publishers between March 2021 and July 2023 to scrutinise the performance of TAs and publisher OA strategies. However, transparency on how OA publishing charges are costed remains elusive; most TA publishers do not provide UK institutions or Jisc with detailed expenses and revenue breakdown. As of July 2023 only nine¹⁶ of the 38 TA publishers had submitted data to cOAlition S's Journal Comparison Service (JCS)¹⁷.

Similarly there is a lack of transparency on OA strategies for most (26) publishers. Seventeen of the TA publishers did not respond to our survey. Eight publishers that did complete our survey do not have (or could not disclose) an OA strategy or definitive targets/timescales to flip journals or portfolios to OA. Three publishers that were without a clear roadmap (or were unable to disclose one) were keen to stress that this does not reflect a lack of commitment to OA.

TAs enabled the UK to achieve an exceptionally high level of compliance with funder OA policies – over 93% of UKRI-funded articles have a compliant route available to them and, of these, 63% can be compliant through a Jisc-negotiated TA.

TAs are not capturing all UK research output

We found that the 'reach' of UK TAs was more limited than we hoped, both to articles from Jisc member institutions and articles published by researchers outside UK HE. There were 168 Jisc member research organisations with CAs that published in TA titles but not all members subscribe to all the relevant TAs. Therefore in 2022 21,894 'missed' articles could have been published via the relevant TAs.

In 2022, 81,838 articles were published with a UK CA: 74% of these were from authors at eligible Jisc member institutions, 65% were from authors at subscribing Jisc member institutions and yet only 47% were actually published via a UK TA.

Not only are there missed articles from authors at eligible organisations, there are groups of researchers (for example those in health and social care, commercial R&D settings or independent researchers) that are currently excluded from TAs (25% of UK CA papers in 2022 were by authors affiliated to non-Jisc members). TAs are yet to overcome the challenges associated with providing OA publishing to all researchers – though the potential to achieve this affordably and fairly is being tested by Jisc and the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR).

The OA transition needs to accelerate

TAs use existing expenditure on subscriptions to fund OA publishing. For this reason it was hoped that as institutions took up more TAs this would stimulate a broader, global transition from the subscription/paywall system to full and immediate OA to all research.

Since the first TA was registered in the ESAC Registry in 2014 the number of TAs and the number of subscribing institutions and countries has grown, with 878 TAs registered as of December 2023. However, the growth in TAs being agreed and registered has slowed, which may indicate that the largest publishers have already made agreements with the countries/consortia most willing/able to enter into them.

Recognising that a large proportion of research originates from research-intensive countries, such as China and the US (26% of all global articles in 2022¹⁸), we considered the impact if these countries had a similar pattern of transition to the UK. Our illustrative calculations suggest that even if these countries adopted TAs they would be unlikely to prompt a transition of publishers' portfolios to OA.

We also examined the article coverage of TAs entered into globally in 2022 ([section 2](#)). Nine publishers had a large number of global TAs (more than ten) but low levels of their global article output were covered by the TAs – less than, or equal to, 0.5% for each. Unless these TAs are extended to cover a broader range of the publishers' output these TAs are unlikely to convert these publishers' portfolios to fully OA.

Author behaviour appears to have remained the same

The availability of TAs across a broader range of publishers in this period does not appear to have changed author behaviours and UK authors continue to choose traditional publishers to disseminate their research.

The top ten publishers account for just over 90% of UK Hybrid output – a higher consolidation than for Closed (78% of output) and for fully Gold (66% of output). The top four publishers (Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley and T&F) together account for just under 50% of all articles published. The consolidation of output with the top four publishers is greater for the Hybrid route (66%) compared to the Gold (c. 25%) and Closed (58%). It is unclear whether TAs are contributing to this consolidation.

Conclusion

Our critical review of TAs provides a timely and comprehensive dataset to inform future discussions about models to support open research dissemination. It is clear that although TAs provide many benefits and have supported UK research to be disseminated in compliance with funder policy there are unintended consequences and negatives that must be considered and addressed.

It is also important to note that, while the review itself provides an objective data analysis it sits within the context of growing discontent with TAs from some institutions. In particular, we have witnessed an erosion in confidence that TAs will achieve a transition within an acceptable timescale. Stakeholders are concerned that without transparency and commitments from publishers TAs will simply become the norm. Given the level of public funds being invested in TAs, and the continual reliance on the UKRI block grant, it is appropriate to review the data and consider if what was considered a temporary investment is efficiently and effectively achieving a transition to OA.

We hope that the data presented in this review will stimulate discussion and debate across the research community about the future opportunities for research dissemination, what success looks like and the actions required to achieve this. We have purposely not suggested what success might look like, but instead we focus on some immediate recommendations:

- To maximise participation in research creation and dissemination without financial or other equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) barriers we recommend that the sector prioritise agreeing additional indicators that demonstrate a commitment to equity. This will help to build support for alternatives to article or APC-based models
- Institutions and funders should use the review's findings alongside other indicators (including public commitments to an OA transition) in addition to the new equity indicators above when defining the research services the sector values and when agreeing where to invest. This includes reducing complexity and demonstrating a commitment to rapidly removing paywalls, while ensuring that models including TAs and successors to TAs do not place (or risk placing) other barriers – such as cost – to participation in research
- Financial divestment from underperforming TAs should be used to provide support for alternatives models. This may also include the redeployment of staff working on the financial or workflow administration of TAs

We hope that these recommendations will enable the sector and the broader research community to build on some of the successes of TAs while discussions take place regarding the future of research dissemination.

Endnotes

- 1 ESAC (no date b)
- 2 Aviv-Reuven and Rosenfeld (2021)
- 3 For a definition of an Open article and other article types, please refer to the [Glossary](#)
- 4 Journals are also classified according to the ANZSRC taxonomy but expanded based on Delta Think's own work on classifying health sciences journals. For more information please see [appendix 2: methodologies](#).
- 5 For a definition of Embargo, please refer to the [Glossary](#)
- 6 See [section 2b 'UK findings: how has the UK conversion to Open Access differed across subject areas?'](#)
- 7 To ensure a fair comparison, only institutions that subscribed to the pre-TA agreement and the current agreement have been included, and only publishers with a subscription agreement (ie, not a TA) later than 2018 but before their TA were included (thereby excluding Springer Nature).
- 8 We acknowledge that cost avoidance as a measure becomes less relevant as alternative means of OA publication grow that would not rely on the payment of an APC.
- 9 Vernon et al. (2021)
- 10 UKRI (2020)
- 11 Based on articles published between 2017 and 2021, which were funded by one of the UKRI funding bodies. Data sourced from [Dimensions](#) in April 2022, an inter-linked research information system provided by Digital Science.
- 12 For a definition of REF-eligible, please refer to the [Glossary](#)
- 13 Data Source: Dimensions
- 14 Jisc (no date d)
- 15 Wiley, Sage, T&F and Elsevier
- 16 European Respiratory Society, IWA Publishing, Royal College of General Practitioners, Royal Society of Chemistry, The Company of Biologists (CoB), The Rockefeller University Press (Rockefeller), Royal Society, Wiley
- 17 See [Journal Checker Tool](#).
- 18 Based on the number of articles published in 2022 with a research organisation in China or the US, but excluding articles with a research organisation in the UK, sourced from [Dimensions](#) on 22 August 2023.

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we are ready to discuss any, or all aspects contained within this report.

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